

INTERFACTICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF Al/Cu COMPOSITE MATERIALS DURING SOLID-STATE DEFORMATION PROCESS

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1. Introduction

According to the recent technology innovation of industry and improvement of living level, the technical requirements on the net shape of metallic material have been strict. Therefore, multi-functional characteristics are required for diverse applications. [1] Metal matrix composites (MMCs) have been recognized as suitable materials to meet such requirements.

However, conventional MMCs manufacturing process, especially liquid phase process have some problems such as volume fraction limitation of the reinforcements, controlled cell size and unstable interface between matrix and reinforcements. Solid state processes have been intensively investigated because it is relatively flexible to overcome such limitations compared to liquid phase process. In spite of the advantages of the solid state process, its main drawback is high processing cost due to usually expensive powder raw materials, complicate processing step and long process time. But, there is an opportunity to overcome such problems by applying a hydrostatic extrusion process which can easily control cell size and volume fraction of the reinforcements as well as the nature of the interfaces between matrix and reinforcement. During the hydrostatic extrusion of clad material, intermetallic compounds can be generated at the interface and acts as reinforcement. Multiple extrusion process after stacking of extrudates could form well aligned second phase in matrix having reinforcement. Hence, it is very important to control interfacial reaction

Al alloy (Al6061)	Mg	Si	Cu	Cr	Al
	1.0	0.6	0.3	0.2	Bal.
Copper (DHP)	P			Cu	
	0.015-0.04			Bal.	

Table 1. Chemical composition of Al and Cu (wt. %)

which may cause formations of brittle phases during the thermal deformation process. [2]

In this study, intermetallic compound formation at the interface between copper and aluminum during extrusion process was simulated by using solid state diffusion bonding experiment according to various processing parameters such as applied pressure, heat treatment temperature and Ag colloid layer insertion between clad layers. These experimental data will be used to set up processing parameters to prepare Al/Cu matrix composite materials by hydrostatic extrusion process.

2. Experimental

2.1 The formation of intermetallic compounds

Square shaped specimens (6 mm x 6 mm x 5 mm) were machined from deoxidized high phosphorus copper (DHP) and aluminum alloy(Al 6061). The chemical compositions of the base metals are shown in Table. 1.

The specimen surfaces were prepared by conventional grinding techniques with final grinding on #1200 emery paper. Then, all specimens were previously cleaned with acetone in an ultrasonic bath. After ultrasonic cleaning, a specimen was loaded in the clamp (Fig. 1(a)) and compression pressure was regulated by torque wrench (Fig. 1(c)). Bearing was used to prevent distortion of the specimen (Fig. 1(b)). The working limits of each parameters were depicted-

No	Bonding Tem. (°C)	Bonding Pressure(MPa)	Holding Time(Hour)
1	400	240	1
2	420	240	1
3	440	240	1
4	460	240	1
6	400	300	1
7	400	360	1

Table 2. Bonding parameters of Al/Cu.

Fig. 1 (a) Bonding clamp; (b) Bearing; (c) Torque wrench

ed Table 2. [3] The specimens were heated up to the bonding temperature in a vacuum furnace (degree of vacuum was 10^{-2} torr) at a heating rate of $5^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ and the required pressure was applied. After bonding, the samples were cooled to room temperature before removal from the vacuum furnace.

2.2 Effect of silver colloid

Two different samples were prepared, sample 1 is Cu-Al, sample 2 is Cu-Ag colloid-Al. Water based Ag colloid with 10,000 ppm of concentration was used for doping. Samples for bonding were heat treated to 400°C and kept for 1 hour in vacuum with 10^{-2} torr, then heat treated at 415°C for from 1 hour to 6 hours to see interfacial diffusion characteristics.

2.3 Interface properties

After bonding, a cross-section was polished and the microstructure was examined by field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM). The chemical composition and the diffusion layer thickness at the interface were analyzed by energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). Furthermore, the mechanical property of diffusion layer itself was examined by means of a Vickers hardness tester.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Effect of temperature on intermetallic compound formation

Fig. 2 shows SEM image of Al/Cu interface that had undergone a heat treatment at different temperatures. There is no any reaction layer in the sample heat treated at 400°C while the thickness increases with the temperature. It should be noted that the interfacial strength seems to be very weak due to the fact that debonding is generally observed at the interfaces in all specimens. Fig. 3 reveals that thickness of intermetallic compounds and hardness of interface increase with increasing the bonding temperature. It is also evident that the thickness of intermetallic compounds and hardness of interface layer closely related with bonding temperature.

Fig. 2 SEM image of Al/Cu interface at different temperature (240MPa) : (a) 400°C ; (b) 420°C ; (c) 440°C ; (d) 460°C

Fig. 3 Results of different temperature (240MPa) (a) Hardness of interface; (b) Thickness of intermetallic compounds

Fig. 4 EDX results near the interface between the Cu and Al for sample heat treatment at 440°C (240MPa)

When the bonding temperature increased significant amount of Cu atoms and Al atoms diffuse into Al and Cu counterpart. Then, form the intermetallic compound, which leads to the thickness increases of the interfacial reaction layers. The slight decrease of the hardness at 460 °C can be interpreted that with temperature increases over a certain level, the width of brittle intermetallic considerably increases and the embrittlement effect over-balances the positive effect obtained due to the improvement in coalescence of faying surfaces as reported by Mahendran et. al. [4].

Fig. 4 shows the EDX results for the Al and Cu interface of the samples heat treatment at 440 °C. Based on these data, the compounds of copper and aluminum sides are composed of Cu_2Al and Al_2Cu intermetallic compounds respectively. And intermediate region is believed to be AlCu intermetallic compounds.

3.2 Effect of bonding pressure on intermetallic compound

The bonding pressure was applied in order to secure a tight contact between the bonding surfaces and a simulated condition of hydrostatic extrusion for the inter-diffusion of atoms of the metals joined. Fig. 5 shows SEM image of Al/Cu interface that had undergone a bonding at different pressure. It was found that intact bonding was not achieved with 240 MPa of applied pressure without any diffusion layer whereas diffusion layer thickness increases with applied pressure increases. Fig. 6 shows the variations of thickness of intermetallic compound layer and hardness of interface with increasing the bonding pressure. If the bonding pressure is less than a certain value, separation of the interface occurred. It

Fig. 5 SEM image of Al/Cu interface at different pressure (400°C) : (a)240MPa; (b)300MPa; (c) 360MPa

Fig. 6 Results of different pressure (400°C) (a) Hardness of interface; (b) Thickness of intermetallic compounds

Fig. 7 SEM image of Al/Cu interface ((a)~(c)) and Al/Ag colloid/Cu interface((d)~(f)) at different holding time (415°C): (a, d) 1hour; (b, e) 3hours; (c, f) 6hours

Fig. 8 EDX results near the interface between Al/Cu and A/Ag colloid/Cu for samples holding time at 1 hour to 6 hours (240MPa, 415°C)

can be seen that the thickness of intermetallic compounds and interface hardness increase with increasing the bonding pressure regardless bonding temperature. This is because the bonding surfaces are never perfectly smooth; they are always rough to some extent. When such surfaces are brought together with low applied pressure, they contact only at the protrusions on the bonded surface, so the contact rates of the bonded joint lower. Generally when the bonding pressure is applied, the points of contact between the two surfaces expand almost instantaneously. The voids formed at the original interface disappear as the contact area expands with time, because the stress within the contact zone causes a plastic flow by either conventional creep or super plasticity. This obviously increases the interface contact rate and the atoms pass through this bonding interface. Therefore, more diffusion paths are created due to the movement of atoms as described in ref. [5].

3.3 Effect of Ag colloid on intermetallic compound

Fig. 7 shows SEM image of Al/Cu interface and Al/Ag colloid doping/Cu interface for a sample heated at 415°C with increasing holding time range from 1 hour to 6 hours. There was a drastic change in the interface layer condition before and after doping of Ag colloid. As shown in Fig. 7(a)~(c), unsta-

ble and debonded interfaces can be clearly observed. But, Fig.7 (d)~(f) shows that sound and intact interfaces are formed. In order to reveal the effect of Ag colloid layer, chemical composition was analyzed by EDX. Fig. 8 shows the EDX results for the Al/Cu and Al/Ag colloid/Cu for the samples holding time at 1 hour to 6 hours. Thicknesses of diffusion layers increase with increasing the holding time, and are irrespective of temperature and pressure. The use of silver colloid effectively decreases the thickness of diffusion layer between the aluminum and copper. The effect of Ag colloid increased with increasing holding time. Furthermore, in the case of Al/Cu bonding, significant amount of Cu atoms diffused into Al side, whereas the diffusion of Al atom to Cu side was very effectively limited by using Ag colloid layer. This is very promising results to control the reactivity between metals economically, especially in composite preparation step by using hydrostatic extrusion process.

4. Conclusion

- 1) Thickness of intermetallic compounds and hardness of interface increase with increasing the bonding temperature, bonding pressure and holding time.
- 2) Bonding temperature has greater influence on the formation of intermetallic compound, followed by holding time and bonding pressure.

3) The use of silver colloid has significant effect to decrease the thickness of diffusion layer between the aluminum and copper with increasing holding time.

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References

- [1] C.G. Kang, H.C. Kwon, "Finite element analysis considering fracture strain of sheath material and die lubricant in extrusion process of Al/Cu clad composites and its experimental investigation", *International Journal of Mechanical Sciences*, Vol.44 pp. 247-267, 2002.
- [2] Y.C. Jin, E.S. Hong, Y.S.Kim, M.S.Lee and C.Y. Yoo, "A study on the Diffusion Joining of 7000 Al Alloy", *Journal of the Korean Society for Heat Treatment*, Vol.6, No.1, pp. 9-16, 1993
- [3] S.C. Tjong, Z.Y.Ma, "Microstructural and mechanical characteristics of in situ metal matrix composites", *Material Science and Engineering*, Vol. 29 pp. 49-113, 2000
- [4] G. Mahendran, V. Balasubramanian, T. Senthilvelan, "Influences of diffusion bonding process parameters on bond characteristics of Mg-Cu dissimilar joints", *Transactions of Nonferrous Metals Society of China*, Vol. 20, pp. 997-1005, 2010
- [5] HE P, Feng J C, Zhang B G, Qian Y Y, "Micro Structure and strength of diffusion-bonded joints of Ti Al base alloy to steel", *Materials Characterization*, Vol. 48, pp. 401-406, 2002